

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

California State University, Fullerton
California State University, Long Beach
California State University, Los Angeles

AN EARLY ENTERAL FEEDING PROTOCOL AFTER PERCUTANEOUS
ENDOSCOPIC GASTROSTOMY TUBE PLACEMENT

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

A quality improvement (QI) project was planned to develop, pilot, and evaluate an evidence-based early enteral feeding protocol (EEFP) for patients with head and neck cancer who undergo PEG tube placements in a comprehensive cancer center in California. The purpose of the QI project was to decrease the time between PEG insertion and initiation of tube feeding. The QI project was planned to take place in a 6-bed subsection of the recovery room where patients were routinely kept overnight for monitoring after insertion of PEG tubes by Interventional Radiology.

The iPARIHS framework was selected to guide the planning, implementation, and evaluation of this project. Addressing the three major constructs of the framework, innovation, recipients, and context facilitated the identification of required actions and consideration of potential barriers that may interfere with the implementation of this QI.

Overall, the review of literature supported the early initiation of enteral feeding (EEF). The literature review also revealed that potential complications of EEF are a key element to consider in assessing the success of implementation. Based on the literature, and evidence-based EEFP was developed, a pilot plan was established, and an evaluation plan of the safety and feasibility of the EEFP was created including plan for patient education and follow up. After achieving the multidisciplinary team consensus, a clear procedure and a workflow chart were developed to guide the implementation of EEFP and clarify the roles of the members of the multidisciplinary team (Interventional radiologists, IR coordinator, dietician, registered nurses, and nurse practitioners).

To evaluate whether the EEFP was successful, safe and feasible, three measures were established with the plan to assess these measures prior to the initiation of project and after one month of implementation. The measures included: Length of time-in hours-between insertion of a PEG tube and initiation of tube feeding, the frequency and severity of complications associated with EEFP as assessed on the SIR classification system, and feeding tolerance. A plan for statistical comparison of average time to initiate feeding, rate of complications and incidence of feeding intolerance before and after initiation of EEFP was created along with diagrams and charts to display data and facilitate comparison.

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BACKGROUND

Delayed initiation of enteral feedings after insertion of percutaneous endoscopic gastrostomy (PEG) tubes is still common practice despite research demonstrating the safety and benefits of early enteral feedings (Dubagunta et al., 2002; McCarter, Condon, Aguilar, Gibson, & Chen, 1998). Although there are no formal guidelines regarding the appropriate time to start feedings after PEG placement, it has been customary to delay feedings for 12 to 24 hours after placement. This common practice may have started with surgically placed gastrostomy tubes and has not been updated to account for gastrostomy tubes which are placed using minimally invasive techniques (Bechtold et al., 2008; Choudhry, Barde, Markert, & Gopalswamy, 1996; Dubagunta et al., 2002). Several studies suggest that initiation of enteral feeding after PEG tube placement can be safely performed between one and six hours after the procedure (Dubagunta et al., 2002; Jensen, et al., 2017). However, at the project hospital of this author, the majority of gastrostomy tubes are placed percutaneously, and enteral feeding is withheld for 24 hours after placement. This practice requires patients to stay overnight in a recovery bay for observation.

Percutaneous endoscopic gastrostomy tubes are commonly placed for patients requiring nutrition supplementation for more than one month (Dubagunta et al., 2002; Xu et al., 2016). In a 217-bed comprehensive cancer center in California, these patients include those with head and neck malignancies who are at risk of malnutrition from treatment-related toxicities (Xu et al., 2016). Head and neck malignancies account for approximately 4% of all cancers in the United States (Siegel, Miller, & Jemal, 2017). Chemoradiation, the standard treatment for most of these cancers, is associated with

mucositis, odynophagia, dysphagia, xerostomia, and vomiting (Xu et al., 2016).

Therefore, these patients are at high risk of malnutrition, which reduces treatment tolerance and efficacy while increasing healthcare costs (Xu et al., 2016).

By implementing an evidence-based protocol to initiate enteral nutrition within four hours after PEG tube insertion, providers create an opportunity to discharge patients the same day as PEG placement, thereby eliminating overnight hospitalization and reducing costs for head and neck cancer patients undergoing this procedure. Decreasing length of stay, especially for this group of immunocompromised patients, would also decrease their likelihood of acquiring infections in the hospital.

Purpose Statement

The initial purpose of this doctoral project was to develop, pilot, and evaluate an evidence-based early enteral feeding protocol (EEFP) for patients who had PEG tube placements in a comprehensive cancer center in California. Because of the COVID-19 pandemic, this project was limited to the development of the EEDP and its approval by the institutional review board at the cancer center. Piloting and evaluating of this project will resume once the pandemic is over. At that time, the author will collect patient data on the number of hours from the insertion of a gastrostomy tube prior to the initiation of enteral feeding prior to the implements of the EEFP and while piloting the protocol. In addition, feeding tolerance and complications will be identified and monitored for patients selected for the EEFP.

Supporting Framework

Frameworks are necessary to guide projects, structure change, and promote efficiency (Bonnel & Smith, 2014). The Promoting Action on Research Implementation in Health Services (PARIHS) framework was developed in 1998 in an effort to identify the multifaceted complexities involved in implementing evidence-based practice changes (Harvey & Kitson, 2016). The authors of this framework reasoned that successful incorporation of research into practice is a function of the dynamic and interdependent relationships among evidence, context, and facilitation (Harvey & Kitson, 2016; Rycroft-Malone, 2004). Evidence is defined as research, clinical experience, patient experience, and local data (Rycroft-Malone, 2004). Context refers to the culture and environment where the proposed change is to be implemented (Rycroft-Malone, 2004). It encompasses leadership styles as well as the feedback process that uncovers whether changes are appropriate, effective, and/or efficient (Rycroft-Malone, 2004). Lastly, facilitation involves an individual's role, skills, and attributes that help enable change (Rycroft-Malone, 2004).

Overall, the PARIHS framework emphasizes the need to consider the nature and quality of evidence, characteristics of the setting, and manner in which evidence is introduced into practice (Harvey & Kitson, 2016; Rycroft-Malone, 2004). However, several studies identified limitations in this framework, including its failure to define successful implementation, describe the intended targets for implementation, and acknowledge the key role of individuals in the facilitation process (Harvey & Kitson, 2016). Therefore, Harvey and Kitson (2016) proposed a revised or integrated PARIHS framework, called i-PARIHS.

The i-PARIHS framework (Figure 1) defines successful implementation as the achievement of established project goals (Harvey & Kitson, 2016). This framework is comprised of four key, multi-dimensional, interdependent elements. The innovation construct not only encompasses taking explicit evidence in its original form but also considers the merging of original evidence with practice-based knowledge to suit a particular situation (Harvey & Kitson, 2016). Innovation is characterized by underlying knowledge sources, degree of fit with existing practice and values, usability, and trialability (Harvey & Kitson, 2016). The recipient construct includes individuals and teams who effect and are affected by implementation (Harvey & Kitson, 2016). This construct underscores the impact of those who support or resist change (Harvey & Kitson, 2016). Recipients' motivation, values, beliefs, skills, knowledge, time, resources, and support can significantly impact the adoption of new knowledge into practice (Harvey & Kitson, 2016). Similar to the PARIHS framework, the context construct is characterized by culture, leadership, organizational priorities, policy drivers, and mandates. However, in the i-PARIHS framework, these factors are examined at the local, organizational, and external health system levels (Harvey & Kitson, 2016). Lastly, facilitation is depicted as a dynamic construct that integrates and appraises innovation, recipients, and context. Facilitation stresses the importance of enabling others to act (Harvey & Kitson, 2016). Facilitators must be knowledgeable, flexible, and responsive (Harvey & Kitson, 2016). The ability of facilitators to enable and support change by customizing their approach to a particular need, group, and setting is vital to successful implementation (Harvey & Kitson, 2016).

The i-PARIHS framework was developed as a guideline to effectively incorporate research into practice and will, therefore, be utilized to direct the implementation process for this project (Table 1). The immediate goal of this project is to successfully develop and pilot an evidence-based EEFP. Innovation involves an extensive literature review and collaboration with recipients, including interventional radiologists, the ear/nose/throat team, radiation oncologists, dietitians, case managers, and the post-operative nursing staff. Recipients who influence change will consider the evidence, review existing practices, and identify advantages, trialability, actual and potential boundaries, challenges, and desired as well as undesired outcomes. In addition, local and organizational context must be considered. The leadership support and feedback, particularly, of the interventional radiologist and the post-operative nurses are paramount. Organizational priorities and drivers, such as patient safety, bed capacity, and hospital resources, must also be addressed. The facilitator will be responsible for presenting evidence, communicating practices, gathering support from stakeholders, and creating buy-in for the proposed change.

Table 1

Application of Integrated Promoting Action on Research Implementation in Health Services (i-PARIHS) Framework

Construct	Facilitator Focus	Facilitator Activity
Innovation	Underlying knowledge sources, clarity, degree of fit, likely boundaries, trialability	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Literature Review Concept and stakeholder mapping Assess potential boundaries
Recipients	Motivation, values and beliefs, clinical consensus, local opinion leaders, skills and knowledge, time and resources, collaboration and teamwork	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Meet with interventional radiologists, coordinators, ear/nose/throat team, radiation oncologists, dietitians, case management, and post-operative nurses to establish short-term and long-term goals for project Establish consensus regarding timeframe to initiate feeding post-PEG placement Discuss perceived boundaries and solutions from recipients' viewpoints
Local Context	Formal and informal leadership support, culture, mechanisms for embedding change, evaluation and feedback process	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Obtain formal letter asserting support from Division Chief of Interventional Radiology Determine method for documenting time of initiating tube feeding, including any reasons for delays Meet with recipients, including post-operative nurses, to establish feedback loop for communicating any needed process improvements
Organizational Context	Organizational priorities, leadership and senior management support, system and processes, and culture	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Meet with Director of Advanced Practice Providers to create buy-in for project Appeal to culture of evidence-based practices and drive for nurse practitioners to practice to fullest scope, including process improvement Assert potential benefits, including cost savings, decreased length of stay, and patient comfort at home compared to overnight stay in recovery room
External Context	Policy drivers and priorities, incentives and mandates, inter-organizational networks and relationships	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Global pay period for gastrostomy tube placements is 10 days Review data regarding any new guidelines or incentives to discharge patients sooner

Facilitator Focus and Activity

What the Facilitator Looks at
 What the Facilitator Does

Source: Harvey G & Kitson A (2015) Implementing Evidence-Based Practice in Healthcare: A facilitation guide. Abingdon, Oxon: Routledge

Figure 1. Integrated Promoting Action on Research Implementation in Health Services (i-PARIHS) Framework

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Overview

A review of literature on the safety and tolerability of early enteral nutrition after gastrostomy tube placement is presented in this chapter. The literature review was conducted using PubMed, CINAHL, and Cochrane Library databases (Table 2). Databases were searched for articles in the English language published between 2009 to 2019. Search terms included percutaneous endoscopic gastrostomy and early enteral feeding. MeSH terms included enteral nutrition/adverse effects, enteral feeding, tube feeding, gastric feeding tube(s), gastrostomy/adverse effects, endoscopy, radiography, and interventional/methods. Peer-reviewed journal publications comprised the majority of articles selected for review. Reference lists of selected documents were also hand searched to identify relevant publications over an extended timeframe. Articles were excluded based on title and pertinence to the project topic. Table 3 outlines the evidence presented in eight key research articles relevant to the safety of early initiation of gastrostomy tube feedings that formed the basis from which the EEFPP was developed.

Gastrostomy Tubes in Head and Neck Cancer Patients

Head and neck cancer is a term used to define a range of malignant tumors that can develop in the organs and tissues of the upper respiratory and digestive tract, including the lips, mouth, tongue, nose, throat, pharynx, larynx, and salivary glands. In addition to cancer cachexia, head and neck cancer patients can suffer from malnutrition due to swallowing difficulties caused by tumor obstruction, pain, limited jaw range of motion, or the effects of surgical resection and/or chemoradiation. Malnutrition increases

susceptibility to infection, impairs healing, contributes to fatigue, and may negatively impact psycho-social functions and self-care (National Collaborating Centre for Acute Care, 2006). Although chemoradiation effectively treats locally advanced head and neck cancer, it is associated with severe and frequent toxicities, such as mucositis, taste disorders, dry mouth, nausea, vomiting, and swallowing dysfunction. Toxicities can decrease patients' quality of life, lead to treatment interruptions, and consequently reduce treatment effectiveness (Atasoy et al., 2012). A study by Atasoy et al. (2012) demonstrated that percutaneous endoscopic gastrostomy (PEG) tube placement can increase the completeness rate of concurrent chemoradiotherapy by providing adequate nutritional support and minimizing weight loss.

Although there are multiple methods to place a gastrostomy tube, interventional radiologists at the project hospital use the push technique. This technique involves inserting the gastrostomy tube directly into the stomach by creating a tract from the abdominal surface. First, ultrasound is used to identify the inferior border of the liver. Then, a small nasogastric tube is advanced into the stomach. The stomach is insufflated through the nasogastric tube, and an appropriate window for tube placement is located. Next, the skin and subcutaneous tissue at the site overlying the stomach are injected with a local anesthetic. Gastropexy is then performed. During this step, up to four T-fasteners are inserted into the stomach under fluoroscopic guidance in order to anchor the anterior wall of the stomach to the anterior abdominal wall. This minimizes the risk of peritoneal leakage and prevents the stomach wall from being pushed away during gastrostomy tube placement. A small incision is made adjacent to the T-fasteners, and the stomach is accessed using a needle. Once intragastric position is confirmed with contrast injection, a

guidewire is advanced through the needle and the tract is dilated with a balloon catheter. A balloon retention gastrostomy tube is subsequently advanced over the wire into the stomach. The retention balloon is inflated with 10 mL of sterile water, and the outer retention disc is brought down to the skin. Following tube placement, appropriate positioning is confirmed with imaging and contrast injection through the tube port. The nasogastric tube is then removed. If the T-fasteners do not spontaneously dislodge, they are removed in clinic 14-21 days after insertion.

Although there are alternative methods for placing gastrostomy tubes, the push technique is recommended for patients with head and neck cancer. The push technique allows the PEG tube to be inserted into the stomach without passing the gastrostomy tube through the upper aerodigestive tumor. In contrast, the pull technique involves dragging the tube along the site of malignancy during gastrostomy tube placement. Several studies have demonstrated that the pull technique increases the risk of tumor seeding and subsequent abdominal wall metastases in head and neck cancer patients (Adelson & Duric, 2005; Ananth & Amin, 2002; Cappell, 2007; Fung et al., 2017; Huang et al., 2013; Lin, Lin, Lee, Huang, & Chang, 2016; Sousa et al., 2013).

Early Enteral Nutrition

Enteral feeding refers to the administration of nutrients directly into the stomach via a tube, such as a gastrostomy tube. Regardless of the technique used for gastrostomy tube placement, feeding has conventionally been delayed until the next day and up to 24 hours post-procedure. However, multiple studies have challenged this practice, including a randomized controlled trial published as early as 1995. In a study of 57 patients suffering from oropharyngeal dysphagia, chronic poor oral intake, or esophageal cancer,

investigating physicians showed that initiating feeding within three hours after PEG placement was as safe and well tolerated as next-day feeding (Brown, Miedema, King, & Marshall, 1995). Similarly, a randomized controlled trial published in 1996 demonstrated that starting feeds three hours after PEG placement was as safe as waiting 24 hours after placement (Choudhry et al., 1996). This study of 41 male, adult patients assessed vital signs, tube length, gastric residual volume, and incidence of peristomal leakage, bleeding, and infections. The authors found no statistical difference between the group that received early feeding and the group that received feeding the next day (Choudhry et al., 1996). Unlike the study conducted by Brown et al. (1995), this study standardized the type of feeding formula and the rate of administration. Another randomized prospective, controlled trial involving 80 intensive and intermediate care patients showed that enteral feeding within one hour of PEG insertion was as safe as 24 hours after insertion (Stein, Schulte-Bockholt, Sabin, & Keymling, 2002). Although increased gastric residuals were noted in the immediate feeding group, there were no significant differences in the rate of complications, including aspiration, pneumonia, and death (Stein et al., 2002). A prospective observational study by Vyawahare et al. (2013) assigned patients to early feeding within 3 hours after PEG placement versus 16 to 24 hours after placement. The authors concluded that tube feeding three hours after PEG placement was safe and reduced hospital length of stay. Additionally, a retrospective study of 444 patients found that initiating feeding less than or at four hours after PEG placement did not increase complications or 30-day mortality compared to feeding after four hours (Cobell et al., 2014). Lastly, a meta-analysis summarized five studies on starting enteral feeding three hours or less after PEG placement compared to waiting more than three hours. The

authors concluded that there were no significant differences in overall complication rates ($p = 0.47$), death ($p = 0.40$), and gastric residual volume ($p = 0.27$). In addition, the number of patients with significant gastric residuals during the first day of PEG tube feeding was not statistically different (Szary et al., 2011).

On the contrary, McCarter, Condon, Aguilar, Gibson, and Chen (1998) performed a randomized, prospective study aimed at comparing the safety and efficacy of early versus delayed feeding after PEG placement and noted a higher percentage of patients in the early feeding group had increased gastric residual volumes on the first day of feeding. In this study, 112 patients were randomized to either begin tube feeding four hours after PEG placement or 24 hours after placement. Although elevated gastric residual volumes were observed in the early feeding group, this was not correlated with increased incidences of aspiration or pneumonia. The authors ultimately concluded that early initiation of feedings is safe and well tolerated (McCarter et al., 1998). A meta-analysis summarizing six randomized controlled trials and a total of 467 adult patients determined there were no significant differences ($p = 0.63$) in the rate of complications between the group whose tube feeds were initiated four hours or less after PEG placement and the group whose feeds were delayed or started the next day (Bechtold et al., 2008). It is worth mentioning that the study by McCarter et al. (1998) was included in this meta-analysis and therefore Bechtold et al. (2008) also concluded that early feeding may be associated with higher gastric residual volumes on the first day of feeding.

Dubagunta et al. (2002) successfully utilized a protocol to start feedings four hours after PEG tube placement in 77 patients without any significant increase in morbidity or mortality. More recently, Sabir et al. (2014) reported that early initiation of

tube feeding after fluoroscopic-guided PEG placement was well tolerated in oncology patients. In this retrospective study, 113 out of 121 patients successfully initiated feeding between three and six and a half hours after PEG insertion. Those who tolerated the feeding were able to be discharged home on the same day as the procedure. Early feeding was not initiated in eight patients, because five patients did not return to start early feeding, two patients complained of severe pain at the PEG insertion site, and one had a syncopal episode. Within 30 days after the procedure, 15 of 113 patients had minor complications, including tube malposition, tube retraction, pericatheter leakage, tube site redness, and tube site pain. One patient had a major complication involving a rectus abdominis sheath hematoma. However, none of these complications were directly caused by early feeding (Sabir et al., 2014).

Complications

The complications of PEG tube feeding can be classified as mechanical, infectious, metabolic, or gastrointestinal (Blumenstein, Shastri, & Stein, 2014). Mechanical complications include clogged feeding tubes, dislodgement, displacement, kinking, and fracture. Infectious complications include skin infections, aspiration pneumonia, and peritonitis. Metabolic complications include electrolyte abnormalities, hypoglycemia, hyperglycemia, vitamin deficiency, and Refeeding syndrome. Lastly, gastrointestinal complications include diarrhea, constipation, nausea and/or vomiting, cramps, bloating, and gastroesophageal reflux. These complications can be further defined as minor or major using the Society of Interventional Radiology Classification System for Complications by Outcome (Sacks, McClenny, Cardella, & Lewis, 2003). Minor complications require minimal or no therapy, may require overnight admission for

observation, and have no consequences. These include peristomal skin infection or irritation, peristomal leakage, gastroesophageal reflux, vomiting, and diarrhea. Major complications require therapy and hospitalization with potential long-term consequences or death. Major complications include bacteremia, gastric hemorrhage, peritonitis, subcutaneous abscess, and aspiration pneumonia (McCarter et al., 1998).

METHODS

This chapter describes the methodology used to develop, pilot, and evaluate an evidence-based early enteral feeding protocol (EEFP) for patients who have undergone percutaneous endoscopic gastrostomy (PEG) tube placement by an interventional radiologist in a Southern California comprehensive cancer center. The i-PARIHS framework guided the author's focus and process of translating evidence into practice. The development of the EEFP protocol and the proposed piloting, and evaluation of the EEFP, which will occur after COVID-19 clearance is given, are described in this section (see Table 4).

Setting

This project will be conducted in a 217-bed comprehensive cancer center in Southern California. The project hospital has one IR angiography suite, four IR physicians, and two IR nurse practitioners. Some of the IR nurse practitioner responsibilities include patient education, post-procedure care, inpatient and outpatient follow-ups, minor bedside procedures, and coordination of care. Gastrostomy tubes are placed by gastroenterologists, interventional radiologists, or surgeons, depending on the patient's diagnosis and anatomy. None of the services have a formal enteral feeding

regimen post-procedure, but all services routinely delay feeding for 12 to 24 hours after gastrostomy tube placement.

Due to the hospital's consistently high census, patients who are admitted solely for PEG placement in Interventional Radiology (IR) stay overnight in a 6-bed subsection of the recovery area while waiting for the PEG to be cleared for use. This subsection is staffed with one nurse for every three patients. It is usually at full capacity, and oftentimes pre-operative bays are used to accommodate any overflow patients needing extended recovery.

Participants

When the piloting of the EEFP begins, the sample will consist of all adult patients, ages 18 and older, who undergo PEG tube placement in the IR suite in a one month period. The majority of patients will have a form of head and neck cancer. Patients with other diagnoses who are not considered candidates for PEG tube placement with Gastroenterology will also be included. Inclusion criteria are an abdominal pain score less than four out of 10, audible bowel sounds, and stable vital signs at three hours post-procedure. In addition, the abdomen must be soft with no rebound or guarding. The patient must not have fever, nausea, or vomiting. Patients who have abdominal pain of four or greater on a 1 to 10 pain scale with associated nausea or vomiting will be excluded. Patients who were nauseated during PEG insertion will also be excluded.

Ethical Considerations

The Institutional Review Board (IRB) of California State University, Long Beach and the IRB of the project hospital will review this project and approval will be obtained.

The author will gather information from the electronic medical record, and all data will be de-identified and stored in a password-protected computer.

Procedure

1. Developing the Protocol

The author, project lead, took the following steps to develop the protocol:

- Met with stakeholders, including interventional radiologists, coordinators, dietitians, case managers, otolaryngologists, radiation oncologists, and post-operative nurses, to create buy-in and discuss goals of project, timeline, workflow, documentation standardization, and potential boundaries and concerns.
- Based on evidence and stakeholder feedback, the author drafted the protocol and established the inclusion and exclusion criteria.
- The author then presented the draft to stakeholders and made additional revisions based on feedback.
- The protocol was finalized, and all stakeholders were notified of the expected implementation date.
- Workflow charts will be distributed to all stakeholders (Appendix A).

2. Piloting the Protocol

The following protocol will be used during the pilot period of this evidence-based practice change:

- Order for IR gastrostomy tube placement is electronically submitted by the referring team (Radiation Oncology, Otolaryngology, General Surgery,

Gastroenterology, Medical Oncology).

- An IR coordinator obtains the order and emails an IR physician and the nurse practitioners for review and approval to schedule case.
- The dietitians and case managers will be emailed to notify them of potential PEG placement date and time.
- The procedure date and time will be confirmed with the patient, dietitians, and case managers.
- The dietitian will arrange to see patient for consultation prior to PEG placement or on the day of PEG placement.
- The patient will undergo PEG placement in the IR suite.
- Post-procedure, outpatients will be transferred to the recovery area for monitoring while inpatients will be transported back to their unit.
- The patient will refrain from having anything by mouth or through the PEG tube for three hours.
- Three hours after PEG insertion, the patient will be assessed by an IR nurse practitioner.
- The PEG tube will be flushed with 30 mL sterile water and cleared for trial feeding if the following criteria are met:
 - Stable vital signs
 - Audible bowel sounds
 - Abdominal pain level less than four out of 10
 - Soft abdomen with no rebound or guarding
 - Absence of fever, nausea, or vomiting

- Volume and rate of trial feeding will be ordered based on dietitian recommendations.
- Vital signs will be assessed every 30 minutes during trial feeding and one hour after trial feeding is complete.
- Feeding will be stopped immediately, and the patient will be evaluated by a member of the IR team if the patient experiences increased abdominal pain, nausea, vomiting, diaphoresis, or significant changes in vital signs.
- While piloting the EEFP, both inpatients and outpatients will be observed overnight and reassessed the day after PEG placement.
- After the pilot period, outpatients who tolerate trial feeding will be discharged home with an in-person or telephone follow-up the next day.
- All patients will be discharged with home health and standard instructions on using the PEG tube and when to seek medical attention (Appendix B).
- The patients will be seen by the IR nurse practitioner 14 to 21 days post-procedure for follow-up and removal of T-fasteners.
- Any complications will be documented and graded according to The Society of Interventional Radiology Classification System for Complications by Outcome (Sacks et al., 2003, Appendix C).

3. Evaluating the Protocol

The author will take the following steps to evaluate the protocol:

- Obtain a chronological list of patients who underwent PEG placement in the IR suite beginning three months before piloting the EEFP and while piloting

the EEFP.

- Review charts and extract the following data:
 - Age
 - Gender
 - Primary Diagnosis
 - Reason for PEG placement
 - Method of PEG placement
 - Size of PEG tube
 - Time PEG was inserted
 - Time PEG was cleared for use
 - Feeding start time
 - Discharge time if outpatient
 - Reasons for delays, if any
 - Complications, if any
 - Increased abdominal pain
 - Increased abdominal distension
 - Nausea or vomiting
 - Diaphoresis
 - Malfunctioning gastrostomy tube

Measurements

Time to Start Tube Feeding

The author will calculate the number of hours from PEG insertion to initiation of tube feeding three months prior to implementation and while piloting the EEFP (see Figure 2).

Complications

The author will monitor for complications, such as infection, bleeding, leakage of gastric contents, ulceration, aspiration, dislodgement, and peritonitis. The frequency of each complication will be calculated one month prior to implementation and while piloting the EEFP (see Figure 3).

Feeding Tolerance

The author will monitor for signs and symptoms of feeding intolerance, such as abdominal distention, abdominal pain, nausea, or vomiting. The number of patients who do not tolerate feeding will be calculated one month prior to implementation and while piloting the EEFP (see Figure 4).

Data Analysis

The author will collect pre-implementation and post-implementation data. The average time from PEG insertion to initiation of tube feeding will be compared at baseline and post-implementation. In addition, the rate of complications and feeding intolerance will be monitored and documented.

Discussion

The purpose of this doctoral project was to develop, pilot, and evaluate an evidence-based early enteral feeding protocol (EEFP) for patients who had PEG tube placements in a comprehensive cancer center in California. Several factors interceded to prevent the completion of this project as conceptualized. However, the protocol was revised, the author obtained IRB approval, the stakeholders were committed to the project, and indispensable knowledge was gained by the author about the Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) Essentials.

During the course of this project, a world pandemic (COVID-19) transformed the landscape of healthcare, especially for the oncology population. This pandemic presented grave consequences and prevented the implementation of the project. At the time that this proposal was under submission, one study documented a 28.6% mortality rate of COVID-19 among 28 patients who were included in the study; the severity of COVID-19 increased if patients received anti-tumor treatments within the previous 14 days (Zhang, et al., 2020). All non-essential care was stopped, and attention was directed to the mitigation of COVID-19 and the preservation of life, including at the facility where this project was planned.

That said, all of the DNP essentials of the American Association of College of Nursing were completed within the context of this project. Although all the essentials were met, in an effort at brevity, only the activities specific to three of the essentials are described in this paper: scientific underpinnings for practice (Essential I), clinical scholarship and analytical methods for EBP (Essential III), and the importance of interprofessional collaboration (Essential VI).

The care of patients who require enteral feeding through PEG tubes is based on integrating the scientific knowledge of anatomy, pathophysiology, nutrition, and psychology, as well as practice regulations and policies or norms at the settings where nurses practice. With that knowledge in mind, the author saw an opportunity to decrease patients' length of stay after PEG tube insertions and increase patients' comfort by starting early enteral feedings (EEF) while at the same time maintain patients' safety. The author collaborated with a librarian and conducted a comprehensive literature search to assess the safety and feasibility of early enteral feeding. In addition, she reviewed and appraised several studies that focused on EEF and assessed the collective body of evidence. Based on the evidence that supports the EEF, the author developed a protocol to guide EEF in collaboration with other clinicians and stakeholders at the facility. In the process, the author honed the skills inherent in Essential I and III which focus on understanding the scientific underpinnings of care and clinical scholarship. The skills of retrieving high quality evidence, and appraising and synthesizing evidence enabled the author to develop an evidence-based protocol that would bring about improvements for the patient and for the facility.

To ensure clear planning and direct steps for implementation, the author identified a framework to guide the process of improvement from the beginning to end, the i-PARIHS model. The framework enabled the author to identify contextual factors on both the organizational and clinician level to facilitate implementation and support sustainability. In addition, the author identified the robust outcome measures to evaluate the efficacy of EEF including length of stay (the time between PEG insertion and initiation of feedings) and potential complications (e.g., peritonitis, leakage). First and

foremost in the authors mind was to evaluate not only the efficacy of the innovation, but also to ensure the safety of the practice change.

This project required extensive interprofessional collaboration to develop the protocol and plan for its implementation. Health care is complex and no single discipline is able to address all the needs of oncology patients facing life limiting disease. In order to meet the project aims as to address the physical, psychosocial, spiritual needs of the head and neck patients served in the project, the author established a team of professionals with a vested interest in patient outcomes. The team included representatives from medicine (interventional radiologists, radiation oncologists, ear/nose/throat team), nursing (post-operative nurses, case managers), administrative coordinators, and dietitians. Because of conflicting schedules, many meetings were held one on one; however, there were also a few conference calls. Strong leadership skills and oral communication skills were employed to facilitate the interprofessional collaboration and thus the progress of the project.

Naturally, interprofessional collaboration supported the organizational and systems changes initiated by the author (Organizational and Systems Leadership for Quality Improvement and Systems thinking [Essential II]). The author presented the project to multiple levels of leadership within the cancer center. Approval was needed from nursing as well as medicine. Although the author's current practice focused on direct patient care, her project will transform and improve the delivery of healthcare for the patient, family and the organization. This project conceptualized a new healthcare delivery system and balanced both the practical realities of the healthcare system with optimal patient/family centered care. The project includes objective measures for

ensuring the safety of patient (the measurement of complication rates and feeding intolerance).

In summary, the foundation for the evidence-based early enteral feeding protocol (EEFP) was established in the time provided for this project. The implementation and evaluation of the protocol will continue into the future. However, the care of oncology patients and the focus of health care was been transformed by the COVID-19 pandemic during the period of this DNP project which precluded the completion of the project as conceptualized. Nevertheless, the work accomplished thus far reflects the advanced competencies required for the increasingly complex practice, faculty and leadership roles that the candidate will face when transforming the landscape of nursing practice.

Figure 2. Simulated Data Graph of Average Number of Hours to Start PEG Feeding

Figure 3. Simulated Data Graph of Percentage of Complications

Figure 4. Simulated Data Graph of Feed Intolerance

Table 2

Initial Search Strategy

Topic	Search Term Combinations	Articles Retrieved	Title Reviewed	Abstract Reviewed	Articles Used
Benefits and Complications of Enteral Nutrition	Enteral Nutrition AND Adverse Effects	392	392	57	10
Benefits and Complications of Gastrostomy Tubes	Gastrostomy AND Adverse Effect(s)	357	357	37	2

Table 3

Evidence Relevant to Safety of Early Initiation of Gastrostomy Tube Feedings

Purpose	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
To compare safety of enteral feedings started at 3 h. vs. next day feedings (Brown, Miedema, King, & Marshall, 1995)	RCT IV: Group 1 feeding began 3 h. after PEG placement. Group 2 feeding began next day after PEG placement DV: starting time to initiate tube feeding, tube feeding tolerance	57 pts total (38 males & 19 females) with 51 pts from inpatient setting and 6 pts from outpatient setting. Mean age: 67 Group 1 (n= 27) Group 2 (n=30) IC: oropharyngeal dysphagia, long-standing poor oral intake, esophageal carcinoma	Rate of feeding intolerance and complications between Group 1 and Group 2	Comparable viability, tolerance, and safety with early feeding and next day feeding	Early feeding was well tolerated and as safe as next day feeding and well tolerated Limitations: Majority of candidates came from the inpatient setting. Comorbidities were not mentioned in the study which could have influenced tube feeding tolerance. Majority of pts were male and do not give a fair reflection of the population.
To assess how quickly a PEG tube can be used after placement (Choudhry, Barde, Markert, & Gopalswamy, 1996)	RCT IV: Group 1 feeding initiated after 3 h. after PEG placement. Group 2 feeding initiated 24 h. after PEG placement.	41 patients at the Veteran's Affairs Medical Center, Dayton, Ohio. November 1993 – April 1995 Group 1 (n= 21)	Observed q4 h.: Compared Group 1 & Group 2 regarding residual volume, aspiration of gastric contents, tube site leakage, erythema & bleeding at tube site,	No significant statistical difference between grps. in all outcomes (p >.005)	Introducing feedings as early as 3 h. from PEG placement is safe and convenient Limitations: only involves elderly males. Majority of

Purpose	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
	DV: starting time to initiate tube feeding	Group 2 (n=20) IC: pts referred to gastroenterology unit for PEG EC: no informed consent, risk of mortality during study, endoscopy contraindications, unsuccessful transillumination of abd wall, ascites, organomegaly, coagulopathy, sepsis	tube length change, bowel sounds, abd distention, abd tenderness Additional measurements: 30-day mortality, # of pts alive at end of study, days pts lived after study, # of days from PEG placement to study conclusion		patients came from a nursing home. Study only examined candidates from Dayton Ohio. Limitations do not give a fair representation of the general U.S. population
To investigate safety of early feeding after PEG procedure (Islek, Sayar, Yilmaz, & Artan, 2013)	Prospective RCT IV: Early (4 th h.) vs. Late (12 th h.) feeding after PEG procedure DV: Complications (gastric residue after feeding, vomiting, fever, systemic signs of infection, and LOS)	Akdeniz University Faculty of Medicine, Antalya, Turkey. Pediatric Gastroenterology Unit b/t 1/2010 and 1/2013. 69 pts. total, 35 early and 34 late feeding IC: PEG placed due to oral motor dysfunction or	Wt., LOS, gastric residue after feeding, vomiting, leakage from tract of fistula, fever, systemic signs of infection recorded before d/c Patients kept diary w/ amt. of feeding in e/ meal, vomiting, amt. of gastric residue. Diary reviewed and	First 72 h. = vomiting rare and similar rate ($p=1.00$). Diff. in rate of gastric residue ($p=1.00$), diff. in LOS ($p<0.001$) excl. pts. treated in hosp. for various reasons Both grps. no sig. gastric residue, leakage from gastrostomy fistula,	Feeding at 4 th h. after PEG can be safe in children and w/o complications (gastric residue, peritoneal leakage, peritonitis) Allows for shorter LOS B/c of shorter LOS, parents cont. to get home edu. for feeding w/ PEG

Purpose	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
	Both grps. given same enteral nutrition formula and 50% of goal vol. Visited by nurse at POD 1 and 3. Potential full vol. feed after 48 h.	recurrent aspiration during oral feeding EC: pts. w/ severe gastroesophageal reflux and dysmotility	wt. recorded 1 month after d/c	peritonitis, or aspiration Both grps. sig. ↑wt.	Limitations: Study conducted in Turkey. May not have same efficacy in U.S. population given demographics and food sources.
To evaluate the differences in safety/efficacy between early vs. delayed feeding s/p PEG placement (McCarter, Condon, Aguilar, Gibson, & Chen, 1998)	Prospective RCT IV: Early feeding in group A (4 h.) vs. Late feeding in group B (24 h.) s/p PEG placement DV: gastric retention, aspiration, postprandial diarrhea, bleeding at peg site	Loma Linda University Medical Center, California. Group A (n = 57) & Group B (n = 55) IC: Patients ≥16 yr requiring PEG with life expectancy > 30 days and willing to participate EC: prior gastric surgery, GI obstruction, gastric dysmotility, ascites, infected PEG site, malignant/infiltrative disease on gastric wall, morbid obesity,	Gastric residual volume, rate of: infection (aspiration pneumonia, bacteremia, peritonitis), GERD, stoma leak Gastroenterologist follow up on day 1 & Day 2	Patients receiving early feedings had 1 or more gastric residuals > 50% on day 1 vs. late feeding group (p=0.029) Complications were infrequent with no significant difference between both grps.	There is still safety/efficacy in early PEG feedings considering that higher residuals in early feedings could be momentarily stopped and then resumed shortly after. Limitations: gastric emptying was not directly assessed in patients.

Purpose	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
		anterior abdominal wall scarring			
To compare the efficacy/safety of early vs. delayed feeding in ICU & intermediate care patients (Stein, Schulte-Bockholt, Sabin, & Keymling, 2002)	RCT IV: In Group 1 (early), pts. initiated feedings 1 h. after PEG placement. Group 2 (late) initiated feedings 24 h. after PEG placement DV: rate of gastric wall injury, gastric retention	Trial conducted between January & December 1997 (hospital in Germany). Group 1 (n = 40) & Group 2 (n = 40) IC: intermediate care/ICU patients requiring enteral nutrition for at least 1 month. EC: pts. Not in intermediate care/ICU, chronically ill pts. requiring PEG, and pts. s/p Billroth procedure	Gastric residual volume, rate of aspiration/bleeding/ab d. distention, leakage Gastroenterologist or fellow assessed each patient every 24 h.	↑gastric residual in 13 pts. in group 1 (32%) vs. 11 pts. In group 2 (28%) Within first 3 days, two pts. died in group 1 vs. three pts. in group 2. No significant difference in complication rate/morbidity/mortality between Early and Late feeding	Early feeding via PEG is just as safe as next day feeding. No statistical significance in short/long term mortality. Limitations: Only assessed early feedings among intermediate care and ICU patients.
To compare safety of feeding 3h. vs. 16-24h. after PEG placement (Vyawahare et al., 2013)	Prospective observational study IV: Early feeding in 3h. (Group 1) vs. Late feeding 16-24 h. after PEG placement (Group 2)	110 pts. w/ oropharyngeal malignancies at Tata Memorial Centre in Mumbai. Convenience sample: 55 pts in Group 1, 54 pts in Group 2, 1 pt did not receive PEG	Rate of complications between Group 1 and Group 2	No major complications No statistically significant difference in complication rates in the 2 grps.	Initiation of feeding 3h. after uncomplicated PEG placement is well tolerated and safe and allowed d/c home earlier

Purpose	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
	DV: Complications (infection, peristomal leak, PEG displacement)	due to stridor w/ endoscopy from May through Sept 2006 IC: Pts. with oropharyngeal malignancies w/ moderate to severe malnutrition who consented for PEG EC: none			Limitations: Not a RCT, prone to bias and confounding, low statistical power
Evaluate tolerability and safety of early enteral feeding after PEG placement (Wiernicka et al., 2016)	RCT IV: Early (3h.) vs. late (8h.) feeding after PEG placement in children DV: Tolerance and safety of enteral feeding after PEG placement	6 medical centers in Poland, 100 patients total IC: B/t 1 month & 18 yrs. Medical indication for PEG, informed consent EC: Not eligible for PEG, need for concomitant fundoplication/lack of technical ability to perform PEG placement procedure	Number of pts. who achieve full feed within 48h. after first feeding bolus, rate of complications, duration of hospitalization, gastric residuals	Rate of complications and mortality similar b/t grps.	First study to evaluate tolerance and safety of early initiation of feeding after PEG placement in paediatric patients. Limitations: Protocol development and planned statistical analysis only. No results of study.
Assess if early PEG feeding leads to ↓inadequacy of	RCT	Pts. recruited from 6 medical centers in Poland that included	Number of pts. able to consume a full feed (calculated to	No statistical significance between grps. in regards to	Early feeding (3 h. post-PEG) was tolerated in pediatric

Purpose	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
nutrition during time prior to initial feeding and ↓LOS (Wiernicka et al., 2019)	IV: Group 1 (early) feeding initiated after 3 h. after PEG placement. Group 2 (late) feeding initiated 8 h. after PEG placement. DV: fasting period after PEG placement, hospital LOS	adults/pediatrics, hepatology, and gastroenterology. Group 1 (n = 46) & Group 2 (n = 48) IC: age 1 month – 18 yrs. requiring PEG EC: coagulopathy, intolerance to endoscopy due to laryngeal/esophageal strictures	individual fluid/calorie requirements) within 48 h. of first bolus feed. Rate of complications and LOS comparison between Group 1 and Group 2	complications (p = 0.118) Grps. did not differ in regards to LOS (p > 0.05)	population without ↑ in complications. Early feeding did not ↓ LOS but it did ↓ period of starvation Limitations: Assessed pediatric population in Poland w/ particular feeding formula. May not have same efficacy with U.S. population and feeding supplement.

Notes: abd.=abdominal; amt.=amount; b/c=because; b/t=between; cont.=continued; d/c=discharge; diff.=difference; DV=dependent variable; e/=each; EC=exclusion criteria; edu.=education; excl.=excluding; GERD=gastroesophageal reflux; grps.=groups; GI: gastrointestinal; GT=gastrostomy tube; h.=hour; hosp.=hospital; IC: Inclusion Criteria; ICU=intensive care unit; IV=independent variable; LOS=length of stay; PEG=percutaneous endoscopic gastrostomy; POD=post-operative day; pts.=patients; RCT=randomized controlled trial; sig.=significant; s/p=status post; vol.=volume; w/=with; w/o=without; wt.=weight; yr=year

Table 4

Project Timeline

Month 1	Month 2	Month 3	Month 4	Month 5
<p>Contact clinical educator for Perioperative Services to confirm there is no enteral feeding protocol after PEG placement in project hospital</p> <p>Meetings with interventional radiologists, dietitians, ENT team, radiation oncologists, case management, and post-op nursing staff to create buy-in, identify concerns, potential boundaries, and establish consensus regarding timeframe to initiate feeding post-PEG placement</p> <p>Establish standard method of documenting start time of tube feeds</p> <p>Establish method of communicating reasons for delays and suggestions for process improvements</p>	<p>Prepare IRB applications</p> <p>Write ROL and Methods sections of proposal</p> <p>Work on CITI training</p> <p>Contact project hospital's research protocol analyst in preparation for IRB submittal</p>	<p>Finalize ROL and Methods sections of proposal</p> <p>Complete CITI training for CSULB and project hospital</p> <p>Prepare and present proposal formally at project hospital and with project chair and committee member</p> <p>Submit IRB applications</p> <p>Begin baseline data collection/extraction</p>	<p>Implement EEFP</p> <p>Evaluate adherence to EEFP</p> <p>Continue data collection/extraction</p>	<p>Create tables showing average time of feeding start time prior to EEFP and during pilot</p> <p>Write analysis of data and put proposal in past tense</p> <p>Submit full doctoral project paper</p>

Obtain formal letter of support from Division Chief of IR				
Month 6	Month 7 Make revisions to paper based on project chair and committee member feedback	Month 8 Finalize paper and make poster	Month 9 Presentation at Dissemination Day	Month 10 Finalize clinical hours log

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APPENDIX A WORKFLOW CHARTS

OUTPATIENT IR PEG PLACEMENT

INPATIENT
IR PEG
PLACEMENT

APPENDIX B

DISCHARGE INSTRUCTIONS

Tube Feeding - Intermittent Gravity Drip Method

(Nasogastric or Gastrostomy Tube)

This information will tell you how to use your feeding tube to give yourself tube feedings and medications, and what to do if problems occur. Your nurse will go over all of this information with you and show you how to do each step.

Do this ____ times per day.

A. Gather Supplies *(your actual supplies may vary)*

- Liquid feeding formula recommended by your doctor
- One tube feeding set (container and tubing)
- One 60ml catheter tip syringe
- About 150ml-180ml (5-6 ounces) of clean drinking water at room temperature
- Stethoscope if needed. Your nurse will show you how to use it.
- Hook or clothes hanger to hang the feeding set
- Other: _____

B. Procedure

1. Before starting the procedure:
 - a) Wash your hands.
 - b) Be sure you are sitting up or that your head is higher than your stomach during the test procedure and the feeding.
2. Test your tube:
 - a) Test your feeding tube for proper placement in the stomach
 - Place the tip of a 60ml syringe into the end of your feeding tube and pull back the plunger gently and slowly. You should get a small

amount of fluid (either greenish liquid or formula from the last tube feeding).

- b) If your syringe fills up completely with fluid when you pull back on the plunger, there could be more fluid in your stomach.
- Clamp or pinch your feeding tube and remove the syringe.
 - Empty the fluid from the syringe into a clean cup.
 - Reattach the syringe to your feeding tube, unclamp the tube and once again pull back on the plunger.
 - Repeat until you no longer get any fluid
- c) If you get more than one half your normal feeding amount or more than 150ml of fluid
- Put back **only** 150ml of the fluid then flush and clamp your feeding tube (see next section).
 - Do not take this feeding but wait until the next scheduled feeding time and test again. If you still get more than the predetermined amount, call your doctor or nurse.
- d) If you do not get any fluid or the tube collapses when you pull back the plunger, the tube may be out of place.
- Check placement by placing a stethoscope over your stomach area and use the syringe to inject 5ml-10ml of air into the feeding tube. Listen for the sound of air going in. This sound means the tube is in place.
- If you do not hear the sound of air, this may mean that the tube slipped out of place. **IF THIS HAPPENS DO NOT TAKE THE TUBE FEEDING OR ATTEMPT TO FLUSH THE TUBE WITH ANY KIND OF FLUID.** Call your doctor or home health nurse.
- e) If the tube is in place and you get less than 150ml of fluid:
- Gently push (do not force) the fluid back into the tube and clamp it.

Continue the next steps only if you have confirmed that the tube is properly placed.

3. Flush the tube

- a) Clamp your feeding tube if you have not already done so.
- b) Take the syringe out of your feeding tube and remove the plunger. Put the empty syringe back into the end of your feeding tube.

- c) Pour about **50ml-60ml** (1 to 1 ½ ounces) of water into the syringe. Unclamp your feeding tube and allow the water to flow in. This flushes and cleans your feeding tube. **Do not leave out this step.**
- d) When the water has finished, clamp your feeding tube and take out the syringe

4. Take the tube feeding

- a) Fill the tube feeding set container with the proper amount of formula. The formula should be at room temperature. Open the feeding set clamp and remove all air from the tubing, then reclamp.
- b) Attach the tube feeding set to your feeding tube, and then unclamp your feeding tube and the tube feeding set.
- c) Regulate the flow rate of the formula. It should take about 30 minutes. Some people require a longer time depending on tolerance.

5. Flush the tube again after feeding

- a) When the formula has finished flowing in, clamp your feeding tube and remove the feeding set.
- b) Attach the empty syringe (without the plunger) to your feeding tube and pour **50ml-60ml** (about 1 to 1 ½ ounces) of water into the syringe.
- c) Unclamp your feeding tube and let the water to flow in. Do this again with another **50ml-60ml** water. **Do not leave out this step.** Then clamp your feeding tube and remove the syringe.
- d) Plug your feeding tube and pin it to your clothes or tape it to your skin so that the tube does not hang loose.
- e) Remain in an upright position for at least ½ hour after feeding.

6. Clean the equipment

- a) Clean the feeding set and syringe with warm soapy water. Rinse well and allow to dry.
- b) When dry put it in a clean place for later use.
- c) Replace the feeding set every week or sooner if you cannot clean it thoroughly or is worn out or damaged.

C. Tips for Taking Medications Through Your Feeding Tube

- a) Your doctor or nurse will tell you which medications you can and cannot take through your feeding tube. **CERTAIN MEDICATIONS MUST NEVER BE CRUSHED OR DISSOLVED.**
- b) Pills or capsules that can be taken through the feeding tube should be well crushed and dissolved to avoid clogging your feeding tube.
- c) Liquid medications should be diluted with 30ml (1 ounce) of water before taking.
- d) **DO NOT** mix multiple medications together and take all at once.
- e) **DO NOT** mix your medications in with your tube feeding formula.
- f) **Always flush your tube after taking medications.**

D. Important Points

1. Do not get air into your feeding tube, which may cause gas pains, and bloating. Avoid this by clamping your feeding tube when no fluid is flowing in
2. Always refrigerate unused opened formula. Do not store for more that 24 hours.
3. Prevent clogging of your feeding tube by:
 - a) Rinsing your feeding tube with 100ml (about 3 to 4 ounces) of water after every feeding.
 - b) Making sure open capsules and pills are well crushed and are mixed well with water before putting in your feeding tube.
 - c) Using only a canned formula, reconstituted formula that is well blended, or food that is pureed and well strained.

E. Call your Nurse or Doctor If:

1. Your feeding tube has come out or moved out of place (see section on testing your tube).
2. Your feeding tube becomes clogged, for example if the feeding formula flows slowly or not at all
3. You have diarrhea (loose watery stools) more than six times per day.
4. You are constipated (do not have bowel movements) for more than three days.

5. You get more than 150ml of fluid two times in a row when you test your feeding tube.
6. You have symptoms of dehydration (not enough water) such as dry mouth, cracked lips, weight loss, fever, decreased amounts of urine or thirst.
7. You have nausea and/or vomiting that does not go away.
8. You have unusual weakness, fever, or any other symptoms that are different than how you usually feel.

F. How to Contact City of Hope

City of Hope professionals are available to assist you if you have any questions or need to report any of the problems listed above.

Weekdays, 8:00 am – 5:00 pm

- For Hematology/BMT patients and Peds patients call the City of Hope operator at 626-256-HOPE and ask for your doctor's office.
- All other patients call the City of Hope Nursing Triage Call Center at 626-471-7133.

Evenings and Weekends

- For Peds patients, call the hospital operator at 626-256-HOPE and ask for the pediatrician on-call.
- All other patients call the City of Hope Nursing Triage Call Center at 626-471-7133.

*For questions about a prescription refill or renewal,

Please call our Triage Prescription Refill/Renewal Line 626-301-8304

Resources:

City of Hope Policy and Procedure *Enteral Feeding and Administration*

Springhouse Corporation (2000) Nursing Procedures (3rd ed.). Springhouse, PA: Author

Tube Feeding Syringe Method

(Nasogastric or Gastrostomy Tube)

This information will tell you how to use your feeding tube to give yourself tube feedings and medications, and what to do if problems occur. Your nurse will go over all of this information with you and show you how to do each step.

Do this ____ times per day.

A. Gather Supplies *(your actual supplies may vary)*

- Liquid feeding formula recommended by your doctor
- One 60ml catheter tip syringe
- About 150ml-180ml (5-6 ounces) of clean drinking water at room temperature
- Clean container such as a large cup or drinking glass
- Stethoscope if needed. Your nurse will show you how to use it.
- Other: _____

B. Procedure

1. Before starting the procedure:
 - a) Wash your hands.
 - b) Be sure you are sitting up or that your head is higher than your stomach during the test procedure and the feeding.
2. Test your tube for proper placement in the stomach:
 - a) Place the tip of a 60ml syringe into the end of your feeding tube and pull back the plunger gently and slowly. You should get a small amount of fluid (either greenish liquid or formula from the last tube feeding).

- b) If your syringe fills up completely with fluid when you pull back on the plunger, there could be more fluid in your stomach.
- Clamp or pinch your feeding tube and remove the syringe.
 - Empty the fluid from the syringe into a clean cup.
 - Reattach the syringe to your feeding tube, unclamp the tube and once again pull back on the plunger.
 - Repeat until you no longer get any fluid.
- c) If you get more than one half your normal feeding amount or more than 150ml of fluid:
- Put back only 150ml of the fluid then flush and clamp your feeding tube (see next section).
 - Do not take this feeding but wait until the next scheduled feeding time and test again. If you still get more than the predetermined amount, call your doctor or nurse.
- d) If you do not get any fluid or the tube collapses when you pull back the plunger, the tube may be out of place.
- Check placement by placing a stethoscope over your stomach area and use the syringe to inject 5ml-10ml of air into the feeding tube. Listen for the sound of air going in. This sound means the tube is in place.
- • If you do not hear the sound of air, this may mean that the tube slipped out of place. **IF THIS HAPPENS DO NOT TAKE THE TUBE FEEDING OR ATTEMPT TO FLUSH THE TUBE WITH ANY KIND OF FLUID.** Call your doctor or home health nurse.
- e) If the tube is in place and you get less than 150ml of fluid:
- Gently push (do not force) the fluid back into the tube and clamp it.

Continue the next steps only if you have confirmed that the tube is properly placed.

3. Flush the tube

- Clamp your feeding tube if you have not already done so.
- Take the syringe out of your feeding tube and remove the plunger. Put the empty syringe back into the end of your feeding tube.
- Pour 30ml-50ml (about 1 to 1 ½ ounces) of water into the syringe. Unclamp your feeding tube and allow the water to flow in. This flushes and cleans your feeding tube. **Do not leave out this step.**
- When the water has finished, leave the syringe in place and go on to the next step.

4. Take the tube feeding

- a) Pour the formula into the syringe (plunger removed) and allow it to flow slowly. The formula should be at room temperature. Raising or lowering the height of the syringe will help you to regulate the speed of the flow.
- b) DO NOT force the formula in with the plunger.
- c) Refill the syringe when it is about $\frac{1}{4}$ full to avoid getting air into your stomach.
- d) Repeat until all formula is finished. It should take about 30 minutes. Some people require a longer time depending on tolerance.

5. Flush the tube again after feeding

- a) When the formula has finished flowing in, pour 30ml-50ml (about 1 to 1 $\frac{1}{2}$ ounces) of water into the syringe and let it flow in. Do this again with another 30ml-50ml of water. **Do not leave out this step.** Then clamp your feeding tube and remove the syringe.
- b) Plug your feeding tube and pin it to your clothes or tape it to your skin so that the tube does not hang loose.
- c) Remain in an upright position for at least $\frac{1}{2}$ hour after feeding.

6. Clean the equipment

- a) Clean the syringe with warm soapy water. Rinse well and allow to dry.
- b) When dry put it in a clean place for later use.
- c) Replace the syringe every week or sooner if you cannot clean it thoroughly or it becomes worn out or damaged.

C. Tips for Taking Medications Through Your Feeding Tube

- a) Your doctor, nurse or pharmacist will tell you which medications you can and cannot take through your feeding tube. **CERTAIN MEDICATIONS MUST NEVER BE CRUSHED OR DISSOLVED.** If you are not sure, please ask.
- b) Pills or capsules that can be taken through the feeding tube should be well crushed and dissolved to avoid clogging your feeding tube.
- c) Liquid medications should be diluted with 30ml (1 ounce) of water before taking.
- d) DO NOT mix multiple medications together and take all at once.

- e) DO NOT mix your medications in with your tube feeding formula.
- f) Always flush your tube after taking medications.

D. Important Points

1. Do not get air into your feeding tube, which may cause gas pains and bloating. Avoid this by clamping your feeding tube when no fluid is flowing in and refilling the syringe before it empties completely when taking the tube feeding.
2. Always refrigerate unused opened formula. Do not store for more than 24 hours.
3. Prevent clogging of your feeding tube by:
 - a) Flushing your feeding tube after **every** feeding.
 - b) Making sure open capsules and pills are well crushed and are mixed well with water before putting in your feeding tube.
 - c) Using only a canned formula, reconstituted formula that is well blended, or food that is pureed and well strained.

E. Call your Nurse or Doctor If:

1. Your feeding tube has come out or moved out of place (see section on testing your tube).
2. Your feeding tube becomes clogged, for example if the feeding formula flows slowly or not at all
3. You have diarrhea (loose watery stools) more than six times per day.
4. You are constipated (do not have bowel movements) for more than three days.
5. You get more than 150ml of fluid two times in a row when you test your feeding tube.
6. You have symptoms of dehydration (not enough water) such as dry mouth, cracked lips, weight loss, fever, decreased amounts of urine or thirst.
7. You have nausea and/or vomiting that does not go away.
8. You have unusual weakness, fever, or any other symptoms that are different than how you usually feel.

F. How to Contact City of Hope

City of Hope professionals are available to assist you if you have any questions or need to report any of the problems listed above.

Weekdays, 8:00 am – 5:00 pm

- For Hematology/BMT patients and Peds patients call the City of Hope operator at 626-256-HOPE and ask for your doctor's office.
- All other patients call the City of Hope Nursing Triage Call Center at 626-471-7133.

Evenings and Weekends

- For Peds patients, call the hospital operator at 626-256-HOPE and ask for the pediatrician on-call.
- All other patients call the City of Hope Nursing Triage Call Center at 626-471-7133.

*For questions about a prescription refill or renewal,
Please call our Triage Prescription Refill/Renewal Line 626-301-8304

If you have a Home Health Nurse call the number provided by your nurse.

Resources:

City of Hope Policy and Procedure *Enteral Feeding and Administration*

Springhouse Corporation (2000) Nursing Procedures (3rd ed.). Springhouse, PA: Author

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City of Hope
1500 East Duarte Road
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626-256-HOPE (256-4673)
www.cityofhope.org

Tube Feeding-Continuous Infusion Method

(Gastric, Duodenal, and Jejunal tubes)

This information will tell you how to use your feeding tube to give yourself tube feedings and medications, and what to do if problems occur. Your nurse will go over all of this information with you and show you how to do each step.

A. Gather Supplies *(your actual supplies may vary)*

- Liquid feeding formula recommended by your doctor
- One tube feeding set (container and tubing)
- Infusion controller
- One 60ml catheter tip syringe
- About 150ml-180ml (5-6 ounces) of clean drinking water at room temperature
- A clean container such as a large cup or drinking glass
- Other: _____

B. Procedure

1. Before starting the procedure:
 - a) Wash your hands.
 - b) Be sure you are sitting up or that your head is higher than your stomach during the test procedure and the feeding.
2. Test your tube every four hours or as instructed by your doctor:

If You Have a Gastric Tube

- a) Stop the infusion controller.
- b) Test your feeding tube to be sure it is properly placed in the stomach

- Place the tip of the syringe into the end of your feeding tube and pull back the plunger gently and slowly. You should get a small amount of fluid (either greenish liquid or formula from the last tube feeding).
- c) If your syringe fills up with fluid when you pull back on the plunger, there could be more fluid in your stomach.
- Clamp your feeding tube and remove the syringe.
 - Empty the fluid from the syringe into a clean cup.
 - Reattach the syringe to your feeding tube, unclamp the tube and once again pull back on the plunger.
 - Repeat until you no longer get any fluid.
- d) If you get more than 2 times the hourly rate or more than 150ml of fluid
- Put back **only 150ml** of the fluid then flush and clamp your feeding tube (see next section for flushing procedure).
 - Wait one hour and test again.
 - If there is still more than **2 times** the hourly rate or **150ml**, do not take the feeding and notify your doctor or nurse.
- e) If you do not get any fluid or the tube collapses when you pull back the plunger, the tube may be out of place.
- Check placement by placing a stethoscope over your stomach area and use the syringe to inject **5ml-10ml** of air into the feeding tube. Listen for the sound of air going in. This sound means the tube is in place.
-
- If you do not hear the sound of air, this may mean that the tube slipped out of place. **IF THIS HAPPENS DO NOT TAKE THE TUBE FEEDING OR ATTEMPT TO FLUSH THE TUBE WITH ANY KIND OF FLUID.** Call your doctor or home health nurse.
- f) If the tube is in place and you get less than 2 times the hourly rate or 150ml of fluid:
- Gently push the fluid back into the tube and clamp it.

If You Have a Duodenal or Jejunal tube

- a) Omit this step since it is often not possible to get any residual with this type of tube.

3. Flush the tube every four hours or as instructed by your doctor

If You Have a Gastric Tube

- a) Clamp your feeding tube if you have not already done so.
- b) Remove the plunger from a syringe and connect it to the end of your feeding tube.
- c) Pour about **50ml-60ml** (about 1.6 to 2 ounces) of water into the syringe. Unclamp your feeding tube and allow the water to flow in. This flushes and cleans your feeding tube. **Do not leave out this step.**
- d) When the water has finished, clamp your feeding tube and take out the syringe

If You Have a Duodenal or Jejunal tube

- a) Follow above procedure but use only **20ml-30ml** (0.6 to 1 ounce) of water.
- b) Some duodenal or jejunal tubes are very thin and narrow and may need to be flushed more frequently. Your nurse or doctor will tell you how often to flush it.

4. Proceed with the tube feeding

- a) Fill the tube feeding set container with the formula. The formula should be at room temperature. Put no more than a four-hour supply at a time to prevent bacterial growth.
- b) Open the feeding set clamp and remove all air from the tubing. Reclamp.
- c) Connect the feeding set to the infusion controller according to the manufacturer's instructions.
- d) Attach the tube feeding set to your feeding tube, and then unclamp your feeding tube and the tube feeding set.
- e) Regulate the flow rate on the infusion controller.

5. To discontinue the tube feeding (if applicable)

- a) Attach the empty syringe (without the plunger) to your feeding tube and pour **50ml-60ml** of water into the syringe for gastric tubes, or **20ml-30ml** for duodenal or jejunal tubes, and let it flow in. Repeat. **Do not leave out this step.** Then clamp your feeding tube and remove the syringe.
- b) Plug your feeding tube and pin it to your clothes or tape it to your skin so that the tube does not hang loose.
- c) Remain in an upright position for at least $\frac{1}{2}$ hour after feeding.

6. Clean the equipment

- a) Clean the tube feeding set and syringe with warm water. Rinse well and allow to dry.
- b) When dry put it in a clean place for later use.
- c) Change feeding set every **24 hours** or as instructed by your doctor or nurse.

C. Tips for Taking Medications Through Your Feeding Tube

- a) Your doctor or nurse will tell you which medications you can take through your feeding tube. **Certain medications must never be crushed or dissolved.**
- b) Pills or capsules that can be taken through your feeding tube should be well crushed and dissolved before taking to avoid clogging your feeding tube.
- c) Liquid medications should be diluted with **30ml** (1 ounce) of water before taking.
- d) **DO NOT** mix multiple medications together and take all at once.
- e) **DO NOT** mix your medications in with your tube feeding formula.
- f) Always flush your tube after taking medications.

D. Important Points

1. Do not get air into your feeding tube, which may cause gas pains, and bloating. Avoid this by removing air from the feeding set tubing and by clamping your feeding tube when no fluid is flowing in

2. Always refrigerate unused opened formula. Do not store for more than 24 hours.
3. Prevent clogging of your feeding tube by:
 - a) Flushing your feeding tube regularly.
 - b) Making sure open capsules and pills are well crushed and are mixed well with water before putting in your feeding tube.
 - c) Using only a canned formula or reconstituted formula that is well blended.

E. Call your Nurse or Doctor If:

1. Your feeding tube has come out or moved out of place (see section on testing your tube).
2. Your feeding tube becomes clogged, for example if the feeding formula flows slowly or not at all
3. You have diarrhea (loose watery stools) more than six times per day.
4. You are constipated (do not have bowel movements) for more than three days.
5. You get more than 150ml of fluid two times in a row when you test your feeding tube.
6. You have symptoms of dehydration (not enough water) such as dry mouth, cracked lips, weight loss, fever, decreased amounts of urine or thirst.
7. You have nausea and/or vomiting that does not go away.
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F. How to Contact City of Hope

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Evenings and Weekends

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If you have a Home Health Nurse call the number provided by your nurse.

Resources:

City of Hope Policy and Procedure *Enteral Feeding and Administration*

Springhouse Corporation (2000) Nursing Procedures (3rd ed.). Springhouse, PA: Author

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City of Hope
1500 East Duarte Road
Duarte, CA 91010-3000
626-256-HOPE (256-4673)
www.cityofhope.org

APPENDIX C**SIR SYSTEM FOR COMPLICATIONS BY OUTCOME**

SIR Classification System for Complications by Outcome
Minor Complications
A. No therapy, no consequence
B. Nominal therapy, no consequence; includes overnight admission for observation only.
Major Complications
C. Require therapy, minor hospitalization (<48 hours)
D. Require major therapy, unplanned increase in level of care, prolonged hospitalization (>48 hours)
E. Permanent adverse sequelae
F. Death.